

The Sailors' Interrogation and Jonah's Silence

Jonah 1:11

Part of a longer analysis into the pauses in speech in the Bible

See *A Study in Silence*

ABSTRACT

This essay argues that the narrative of Jonah 1:7–11 deliberately mirrors the chaos of the storm through both its structure and Jonah's speech. The rapid succession of overlapping interrogatives conveys urgency, fear and disorientation, while the narrator's non-linear disclosure of information further reflects the tumultuous setting. Against this backdrop, Jonah's response appears fragmented and psychologically strained, revealing an inner conflict between his fear of Jehovah and his resistance to the divine commission. His moment of silence exposes Jonah's moral hesitation, as he withholds fuller disclosure and wrestles inwardly with competing impulses: self-preservation, responsibility and withdrawal. Ultimately, the essay contends that Jonah is portrayed not as a figure of satire but as a psychologically realistic character.*

Jonah 1:11

וַיֹּאמְרוּ אֵלָיו מִה־נַּעֲשֶׂה לָּךְ וַיִּשְׁתַּק הַיָּם מֵעֲלֵינוּ כִּי הַיָּם הוֹלֵךְ וְסֹעֵר

The pause came in the middle of a storm—literal and psychological.

After casting lots for supernatural assistance, the crew of the ship discovered that Jonah was the cause of the storm (verse 7). This led to “a barrage of questions shouted out simultaneously by different voices in their panic in the face of the storm” (Savran): “Do tell us, please, on whose account it is that we are having this calamity? What is your work, and from where do you come? What is your country, and from which people are you?” (verse 8). Savran sees this set of jumbled, overlapping set of questions as evidence of multivocality. “The piling up of questions here, one upon another, creates a mood of excitement and of pressure.

* See Appendix, page 5.

The frequent use of the particles contributes to the rapidity of the speech. Thereby a sense of urgency and of anxiety” (Trible, p. 212). All this accentuated the chaotic situation—the fury of the storm, the huge waves, the hull lurching violently, the intense pressure on the everyone’s life.

The first question, “Do tell us, please, on whose account it is that we are having this calamity?” seems unnecessary since the lots had identified Jonah. However, perhaps the sailors were not prepared to condemn Jonah on the evidence of the lot alone, and sought a confession from him (cf. Josh. vii. 19) (Goldman), or perhaps, since the storm was so severe, they thought that Jonah had upset the gods and he was a pawn of someone more wicked, hence, “on whose account it is?” This might explain why the next question was “What is your work?”. They might have been thinking that his business was illegal.

The next three questions are connected to his place of abode and ethnicity.

In response Jonah said, “I am a Hebrew, and Jehovah¹ the God of the heavens I am fearing, the One who made the sea and the dry land” (verse 9).

After a profusion of questions we tend to address the last one, since by then the first is a distant memory. So Jonah collected the three last questions into one answer: “I am a Hebrew”. One could conclude that “Jehovah the God of the heavens I am fearing” was in answer to “What is your work?”, in other words, I am not a criminal. But there was no confession. Now came what seems like a pause.

10 And the men began to fear greatly, and they went on to say to him: “What is this that you have done?” For the men had come to know that it was from before Jehovah that he was running away, because he had told them. 11 Finally they said to him: “What should we do to you, in order that the sea may become still for us?” For the sea was continually growing more tempestuous.

Verse 10 gives the details in reverse order. We are told that the sailors “had come to know that it was from before Jehovah that he was running away”, then they exclaim, “What is this that you have done?” He had already told them that he was fearing Jehovah, now we are told that the sailors had come to know that he was running *from* Jehovah. Why is this disclosure not presented as direct speech—part of Jonah’s speech? It is as if the narrator is once more mimicking the disorientation of the storm in the way the information is coming to the reader.

If Jonah told them as a result of their question, “What is this that you have done?”, there is no pause in the sailors’ speech for us to investigate.

But what if Jonah had added it to his previous answer and said something like, ‘Jehovah the God of the heavens I am fearing, the One who made the sea and the dry land, and I am running away from him’?

KD believe that Jonah’s statement in verse 9 “is not given completely; but the principal fact, viz., that he was a Hebrew and worshipped Jehovah, is followed immediately by the account of the impression which this acknowledgement made upon the heathen sailors; and the confession of his sin is mentioned afterwards as a supplement, to assign the reason for the great fear which came upon the sailors in consequence”.

If this is true then his statement is convoluted and as others have noted, ironic in its inconsistency—how can Jonah run from the creator of the sea and the dry land? But there is a psychological authenticity in this. Here was a prophet caught in the supreme dilemma—a collision of his fear of Jehovah and his fear of Jehovah’s commission. Later it becomes evident that Jonah struggled with the outcome of the commission (4:2). That created tension: God is merciful—a warning must be given, but that warning could lead to mercy for a people Jonah believed deserved adverse judgement. Holding those two truths at once—justice and mercy—likely produced plenty of inner conflict.

Going down into the ship’s hold and falling asleep resembled a shut-down response. Indeed, three times the verb ירד ‘go down’ is used, twice in verse 3 and once in verse 5—down to Joppa, down into the boat, down into the innermost parts of the boat. When stress becomes overwhelming, people sometimes disengage mentally and physically seeking to hide. Jonah’s descent and finally his sleep could be read as a kind of escape from unbearable tension.

Goitein believes that although Jonah behaved in ways that could be read as ironic or even absurd—fleeing from God—the narrative voice does not treat him as a figure of ridicule. Instead, it presents him with emotional depth and moral realism:

The whole tenor of the story is much too earnest for a satire; Jonah is not painted with the brush of mockery or disdain, but drawn with the pencil of deep and sympathetic insight into human weakness. A careful consideration...seems to indicate that the writing of this book of Jonah is an act of atonement of a man belonging to the prophets who criticises his own conduct with scrupulous thoroughness, leaving, as the author of Job did, the last word to God.

We believe that KD assessment is likely correct, and therefore we have a deliberate confusion in the way the sequence of events is told and in the way that Jonah is expressing himself. All of which is in unison with the confusion of the elements outside the ship.

If then there is a pause, what went on between the sailors saying, “What is this that you have done?”² and “What should we do to you, in order that the sea may become still for us?”? A silence. And a transition from shock to pragmatism.

Apparently Jonah did not want to elaborate further. All that he was willing to divulge was that he was running away from Jehovah. He did not want to tell his interrogators about Jehovah’s command that he was seeking to avoid. It was not just that Jonah feared the Ninevites, he was going through a moral struggle between Jehovah’s mercy and justice, and he just wanted to escape and hide from it all. So his silence reveals his moral hesitation between the safety of the sailors and Jonah’s desire to withdraw completely. That being the case, then he was not going to be able to articulate it to the sailors in the midst of his physical and emotional maelstrom.

Further, now that he had been exposed by God and by the sailors, where now could Jonah flee? In his silence he had possibly been searching for answers to this and how to save the sailors lives. So when the sailors then asked, “What should we do to you, in order that the sea may become still for us?”, he responded, “Lift me up and hurl me into the sea, and the sea will become still for YOU; because I am aware that it is on my account that this great tempest is upon YOU.”

APPENDIX

In the Bible the divine name יהוה occurs almost seven thousand times, more often than any of God's titles, and more often than any other separate Hebrew word.

There are many theophoric names in the Bible. The majority of Bible translators transliterate those names which have the first two syllables of the divine name as Jeho. Hence: Jehonathan, Jehoshua, Jehoshaphat, Jehoahaz, Jehonadab, Jehoram etc. When the Israelites shortened a name they would not abbreviate but they contracted it by removing syllables from the middle of the name. So Jehonathan was reduced to Jonathan; Jehoshua became Joshua; Jehonadab became Jonadab. God's name was contracted to Jah, hence: Elijah, Abijah and Hallelujah etc. Therefore, the divine name must have had three syllables, not two.

We believe that a י is more likely to be transliterated as a y in English, and a ו is more likely to be transliterated as a w. So the divine name could be *Yehowah*. However, most Bible scholars avoid any transliteration. They use the tetragrammaton in Hebrew letters יהוה, or they display the divine name as YHWH. This is all well and good, but it is inconsistent with their transliteration of other Bible names. If they are to be consistent then they should either use Yehonathan for Jonathan or show the Hebrew letters יהנתן, or YWNTN. Sometimes they use *Yahweh* which disregards how names were shortened, and it only has two syllables.

The argument that the vowels of יהוה are those of אֱדֹנָי does not hold up because the vowels are not the same.

Gesenius pointed out that "Those who consider that יהוה was the actual pronunciation [of God's name] are not altogether without ground on which to defend their opinion. In this way can the abbreviated syllables יהו and י, with which many proper names begin, be more satisfactorily explained."

We believe that *Jehovah* is a reasonable transliteration of the tetragrammaton.

ABBREVIATIONS AND BIBLIOGRAPHY

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Bible quotations are from the *New World Translation of the Holy Scriptures, with References*, 1984, unless otherwise indicated.

The Introduction to this edition of NW contains this explanation:

Where “you” is printed in small capital letters, it shows that the pronoun is plural. Also, where the plural number of a verb is not apparent, its plurality is indicated by printing it in small capital letters. If the context already clearly indicates plurality, then no special capitalization is used.